

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

Evaluation Report #2 for **TEBT-2025-0019**

Submission Information Table

Submission Title	Comparative assessment of animal experimentation regulations and the integration of new approach methodologies across six Latin American countries
Submission Reference	TEBT-2025-0019
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley 0000-0003-4021-0785 ▾
Editor Declaration of Interests	The editor is not aware of any conflicts of interest that could compromise their handling of this submission.
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Use of AI in evaluation	DataSeer.ai was used to check the consistency of the data availability statements in the manuscript with journal policies. Prophy.ai was used to identify suitable peer-reviewers for the manuscript.
Recommendation	Revise ▾

Editor's Summary of Reviewer Comments

This article is an interesting and potentially important review of the economic and legal infrastructures around the use of animal and non-animal experimental methods in toxicology in Latin America, using six countries to represent the overall regional situation.

Although major revisions are being recommended, as the authors will see both I as editor and the reviewers clearly enjoyed engaging with the piece and are very supportive of the authors' goals, so they should not be disheartened by the number of comments and depth of revisions being asked for.

Everyone reviewing this paper agrees that it presents a highly relevant and promising discussion. However, issues have been raised about whether the article is sufficiently comprehensive to be representative of Latin America as a whole, while also not being sufficiently complete or accurate to be representative of the national situation in its six target countries. Finding the balance between manageable length with sufficient, accurate detail is going to be challenging.

Since a full account of the current situation in Latin America would fill a very long report, I would recommend the authors reconsider whether they want to provide a review-type article, and instead present a clear and direct argument for their viewpoint (a viewpoint which still needs to be defined) using as evidence well-chosen examples from the wide range of laws, organisations, and companies they are seeking to summarise.

This would allow the article to be shorter and have the desired impact, without necessarily having to present a complete summary of a complex situation in multiple countries - something that appears to be both methodologically and practically unfeasible.

Seriousness of issues identified with described methods	There are important issues with the structure and goals of the general argument, scope of paper, and comprehensiveness and accuracy of observations and claims being made.
Potential additional work to overcome issues	Extensive revisions are necessary but will significantly improve an already interesting and promising article.
Acceptability of characterising limitations instead of further developing the methods	The authors will want to consider what revisions are feasible. The article does not need to cover everything, it is more important that it makes a clear argument within a well-defined scope.

Checklist of minimum required information

Y = Yes, provided | R = Revisions, additions, or changes recommended | X = Not needed or not applicable

#	Status	Item checked
1	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Preprint, relevant revision materials, and supplemental material available on Zenodo
2	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Full name, affiliations, and ORCIDs (if available) of each author are present
3	<input type="radio"/>	Correct institutional co-authorship + email to EiC if official publication of EBTC
4	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Structured abstract has been provided
5	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement have been given
6	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Complete funding details are given, or “no funding” is declared
7	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Informative disclosure of interests for all authors has been provided or disclosure declined
8	<input type="radio"/>	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited, if relevant (TOP 1, Level 3)
9	<input type="radio"/>	Data and code availability is stated and links to both are functional (DAS templates)
10	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	One or more appropriate reporting checklists for submission type have been completed
11	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	Supplemental materials have plain English file names
12	<input type="radio"/>	For Registered Reports submissions, preregistration level clearly indicated

Comments about minimum required information

Key: Numbered according to the checklist items above, e.g. #5 would be a comment relating to declaration of author contributions

#4: It can help the reader if an abstract is structured, i.e. has headings and sections that reflect the structure of the main manuscript. This is not compulsory, but if the authors feel this could improve how the abstract summarises the manuscript, they should edit the abstract accordingly.

#5: The authors should remember to include the author contributions as a section in their manuscript, not just in the cover letter.

#7: The authors should make it clearer in their declaration of interests and the manuscript that the organisation they are from (Te Protejo) is a subject in their own manuscript. I comment in more detail about being objective about Te Protejo below.

Other: I recommend the authors use line numbering and section numbering in their revised manuscript, as it makes it much easier for reviewers to indicate the sections on which they are commenting.

Reviewers' Comments

Note about reviewer comments: Reviewer comments have been aggregated into the structured feedback below by the handling editor. Comments may have been edited for constructiveness or continuity, or annotated to indicate how the authors may consider responding. Comments are numbered for ease of reference.

1. General comments

Editor

1. The article is of clear interest and relevance to discourse around the use of animals and alternative methods in toxicology, and potentially presents some important insights into NAM development in Latin America, a region of overlooked but emerging importance in toxicology. I am very supportive of the authors' goals. In general the motivation of the article is clear and will appeal to the reader.

This suggests the authors could focus on the following: article length; clarifying how the information and views presented are grounded in local knowledge, literature, and other data sources; clarifying its comprehensives; and considering whether there is enough information of the type that would typically be found supporting a review article such as this (e.g. extending data to include economics, employment, legal records, etc.). After a strong first section (up to page 10) the manuscript turns into more of a list of regulations and actors than being the structured, academic accounting of the system and its challenges that I believe the authors are aiming for.

2. One of the reviewers remarked to me that while they believe the study presents a highly relevant discussion regarding the regulatory frameworks of certain Latin American countries, they felt that a more comprehensive approach is needed for the discussion to be truly compelling and to allow for stronger conclusions about the situation across Latin America as a whole.

I am not personally sure of how to interpret this - a more comprehensive summary of

even more countries seems not to be feasible (it would fill a very long report); on the other hand, the presentation of data feels a little bit piecemeal, especially towards the back end of the article. This is why I suggest reconsidering the article as an argument by the authors, which they evidence with carefully-chosen examples, rather than trying to provide a complete summary of a situation on a large and diverse continent.

3. One of the reviewers also concurred with the points raised in the editorial triage report. While the intent of triage is not to second-guess the peer-review process, this does provide some validation of the points I was raising there (and are reproduced in this report).

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 3

4. The overview about the situation of animal experiments in Latin America is very interesting and important. In summary, this overview could be very relevant, but has to be improved significantly for the reader's convenience and to provide more concrete content as well. Otherwise it does not provide enough precise information to understand the situation in these countries better.

2. Hook and focus

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

This article has a strong and engaging introduction that is relevant and timely. However, as an expert opinion, it seems that the authors could be clearer about the point toward which they are arguing. While no reviewers specifically commented on hook and focus, I think overall it is part of the general questions of what it is the authors want the reader to conclude, and how can they get the reader to this conclusion via an argument that pulls together the information they are presenting in their article?

Reviewer comments

Editor (inserted from triage report)

5. At the top of page 4, the authors state "this study aims to characterise" but I am not sure this manuscript strictly represents a study - it is more an informed summary or overview of a situation, by people with expertise in that situation. Overall, in terms of EBT's

submission types, it probably fits best as a comment article.

6. Once the issue of article type and focus as been resolved, I would suggest changing the title to more precisely reflect the content of the article: it is not strictly a comparative assessment (the purpose of the study is not to compare, but to provide an overview), rather it seems to be something more like: "An overview of the regulation of animal experimentation and moves toward use of NAMs in six Latin American countries" (this is a rough suggestion, not a recommended revision).
7. The methods for developing the comment, and therefore securing in the mind of the reader the credibility of the observations being made, need adding. I suggest adding a short paragraph explaining how the authors chose their target countries, how they developed their review of the situation in those countries (even if it was mainly their expertise) and why they are a credible source for the summary they provide (is it their special regional expertise?). The GRADE Working Group develops a lot of expert recommendations, with paragraph 2 of this paper providing an example (I am not suggesting the authors follow this formula, just showing how a concept paper or comment article can still have its methods described).
8. Relating to the scope of the article, it is not always clear when the authors are talking about the six countries they have researched, or when their comments apply to the region as a whole. It is notable that the first 8 or so pages (which is a decent proportion of the manuscript) are about Latin America in general. The point here is just to be very clear about the scope of the article - is it, in fact, an overview of the use of animals in experimental toxicology in Latin America, or is it a specific summary of regulation of animal use in research and moves toward use of NAMs in six countries in the region.
9. The introduction provides a strong summary of the shift away from animal testing, but seems to be lacking reference to other related research about the shift in the region that would help situate this manuscript's contribution to a broader area of research (presumably this paper is not unique - there must be other research on this as well, which has informed the authors viewpoints?). For the introduction, the authors should add a paragraph explaining the context of their paper and how it contributes to knowledge in the field - what else has been done that is similar (if anything) and how

does this contribute?

10. Relating to points elsewhere about the structure of the authors' argument, I am not sure that the conclusions of the article ("The necessity for accurate data on animal use [...] regulations that guarantee the quality of research and animal welfare") are sustained by the information and argument in the article. I don't disagree with the point (it is self-evident), it is just that I don't quite see how the information the authors have presented is an evidenced argument for these final claims. The reader would probably want some more specific information about the structural strengths and weaknesses of the situation in the six example countries so they can anticipate what a response should look like, to interpret the descriptive national summaries into improvements in quality of research and animal welfare. I comment in more detail on this below.

3. Strength of argument

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

I suspect, given the lack of information about the methods for generating the review, what we have is a methodology for creating this summary that may not match the very broad goals of the report. How can we be sure that the review is authoritative, if we are not sure how data was collected? And if the intent is to be authoritative for such a large area, how can data collection ever be satisfactory?

Reviewer 3's comments are symptomatic of this issue, where they helpfully identify quite a large range of issues in the authors' arguments. Again, I am drawn to the idea of presenting an evidenced argument rather than trying to present all the facts about such a complex situation: rather than trying to respond comment-by-comment, I suggest the authors reconsider the goals of the article (again, to avoid a situation where the article is of unmanageable length, makes a number of claims it is impractical to evidence, and in general tries to achieve something unfeasible for a single journal article).

Reviewer comments

Editor (inserted from triage report)

11. In the "biomedical research" section, the authors state that research focuses on "biological mechanisms and developing treatment or potential cures for non-communicable diseases" but nearly all the examples are of communicable disease. The

authors should decide which it is (could it be both?) and provide evidence accordingly.

12. I was going to make a minor comment, then realised it indicated a more important issue in the manuscript. In paragraph 2 of the biomedical research section, the authors state that the increase in animal testing is “contradicted” by the low rate of statistics regarding its use.
13. My minor comment is that I feel the authors do not quite mean “contradicted” - more that, although use of animals is high, reporting of animal use is still low?
14. My major comment is that there is maybe insufficient discussion of the quality of data underlying the observations being made by the authors in the manuscript. If, for example, animal use is not well-reported, what does that mean for estimates of animal use? Do we know, for example, which species are in fact the most used? Is that reliably quantified, or just an educated guess? Sometimes the authors make a factual statement and back it up with a citation (e.g. “it is reasonable to infer that these same four species are still standard in Latin America cosmetic testing before bans and restrictions (Pritchett, 2025)”) but are the authors in fact reporting someone else’s claim? If so, how credible is that claim, and should the authors present it as a fact (as they are currently doing) or should the present it as reporting someone else’s claim (e.g. saying “it is expected that the same four species etc”)
15. Sometimes the authors make claims that are not obviously backed by evidence. They state that “Brazil and Mexico are leading the research into alternative models” as fact, with a citation, but in what sense are they “leading” and on what data is this statement based? Are the authors just reporting someone else’s claim (so, technically, “Brazil and Mexico are *reportedly* leading...”) ? This comes back to the issue of distinguishing between claims made by others, the evidence for those claims, and the claims being made by the authors (and the evidence for those). (Also, the authors should clarify if they mean regionally, or among the six countries they are surveying.)
16. It is not clear to me how the authors selected the countries, regulations and legal frameworks, institutions, experimental centers and facilities, civil society organisations, etc. that they have. It is surprising to me that there are not more counts of the number of

organisations, for example, or economic data showing relative size of sectors or change in size or importance over time. This is especially if the selected organisations and other entities are intended to be examples of national trends within a region - the intended “comparative” element of the work is not really present.

17. The section “Main experimental centers and livestock facilities” (p16): Earlier in the piece, it was stated that it is difficult to track animal use in the target countries and that in general animal use may not be being conducted ethically. As I understand it, this is one of the main motivations of the article, yet here there is only a short list of facilities and no mention that there might be ethical issues in animal use. Are we sure the complete picture is being presented in this manuscript, or are there under-reported activities that are not talked about because they are less visible? Does this imply a need for revisions in the information presented, and/or sections about this issue to more directly connect the content of the manuscript to its motivations?
18. In relation to this point, I would also be interested in hearing more about cumulative use of animals in smaller, less publicly-visible, potentially less well-run centres. How much animal use is accounted for by the larger facilities? Is it most of it, or do the small facilities add up to significant use? If there are ethical concerns, where do the problems appear in the sector? This feels like it may be an oversight in the manuscript.
19. In relation to the alternative methods laboratories in Chile (p18), and also relating to point 6 above: are there only four laboratories? If there are more, why mention these four specifically? I wonder if it would be helpful to the reader, when summarising the national situation, to indicate how many laboratories there are in total (in number, in some measure of economic activity, employment, funding, etc.) and then pick out a few examples that are especially illustrative of the issues the authors are seeking to communicate?
20. On page 19 the authors state “As a result, by failing to establish strict criterion for authorizing experimentation, the law might justify a wide range of experiments”. This may be true, but the claim is not substantiated by the text - my feeling is that for a paper that is motivated by misuse or over-use of animals in research, there is not very much documentation of the problems, such as the gaps in the legal frameworks regulating the

market (the authors list the frameworks listed, but I am not sure they have analysed them) and the behaviour of the market itself. This could help develop the second half of the manuscript from being a list of regulations and actors, as it mainly is from page 10, into a structured accounting of the system and its challenges.

Reviewer 1

21. Why did the authors choose only certain Latin American countries (Chile, Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, Colombia, and Peru) rather than including all countries in the region? For a more accurate assessment of the situation in Latin America, it would be preferable to consider all countries within this territory. At several points in the text, the authors refer to “in Latin America...,” including in the conclusion. How can such a statement be made based on the analysis of only six countries? Uruguay, for example, like Brazil and Mexico, also has specific legislation regulating the use of animals in teaching and research activities.
22. The authors state that “In most countries, except for Mexico (SAGARPA, 20), it is not a legal requirement to declare the number of animals used in experiments nor the number of procedures performed on animals annually to an official institution.” This information is incomplete. In Brazil, according to [Normative Resolution No. 51 of 2021 issued by CONCEA](#), researchers are required to provide institutional ethics committees with detailed information on teaching and research projects, including data concerning the animals used. These committees, in turn, submit annual reports containing such information to CONCEA, the Brazilian regulatory authority.
23. Regarding Argentina, it is worth noting that, in pursuit of specific legislation, the Argentine Association of Laboratory Animal Science and Technology (AACyTAL) began drafting a bill in 2012 aimed at regulating the use of animals for scientific and educational experimentation (Law for the Protection of Experimental Animals Used for Scientific and Educational Purposes). In 2016, this bill was submitted to the Chamber of Deputies and was approved in 2017, after which it was forwarded to the Senate for consideration; however, it was not enacted. At the end of 2018, the bill lost its parliamentary status, requiring it to be reintroduced for approval. Oversight of teaching and research activities involving the use of animals in the country has been carried out voluntarily by institutional ethics committees nationwide. These committees have played

an extremely important role in ensuring the ethical use and welfare of animals.

24. With regard to Brazil, in the section “Regulations and Legal Frameworks,” it would be appropriate to mention that, in addition to the regulatory instruments already cited, the country also has numerous Normative Resolutions (NRs) and Technical Guidelines (TGs) which, together with Law No. 11.794 and Decree No. 6.899, regulate the use of animals in teaching and research activities (10.30802/AALAS-JAALAS-24-157). These NRs and TGs, issued by CONCEA, also address alternative methods recognized in the country, such as NRs 46 and 55, among others. It would also be relevant to mention the Brazilian Center for the Validation of Alternative Methods (BRACVAM), whose primary focus is on activities related to alternative methods to animal use in research and education.

Reviewer 2

25. This is a well-researched and valuable review of the status quo with respect to animal research, its regulation and the use of NAMs, in six Latin American countries. The disparities among the countries are clear. Having them spelled out like this works effectively as a call for homogenization. Less clear is how that might be achieved. The content is there, but the delivery might be improved. The main points could be made more concisely, and arguably more persuasively, in a much shorter article, for instance, using tables to make direct comparisons across the six countries and using open-access archives for supplementary data. **[Editor’s note:** This comment reinforces my sense that there needs to be a clearer argument that the authors build towards, carefully choosing from the information they have gathered the evidence for what they are arguing toward, presenting data efficiently in tables and charts as well as narrative text.]

Reviewer 3

26. What is clearly missing is an overview of animal numbers used in the respective countries and middle/south America in total. Also an estimate about the different species and fields such as basic research, translational/applied research and regulatory applications. Are there really no data estimates available ? **[Editor’s note:** It seems to me that providing data for and clarifying every point that Reviewer 3 makes is not feasible - rather, the answer is to construct a more focused paper, reducing the scope and number of claims that have to be evidenced.]

27. Line 17: veterinary medicine is excluded/not mentioned, in which certainly animals as patients and experiments make sense.
28. Line 34: is it really a universal human value ? authors forget/do not mention e.g. cultural differences, animals are totally differently perceived e.g. in Asian regions.
29. Line 38: Where are the 3Rs principles recognized as a scientific framework, this is not globally perceived like this.
30. Line 47: EU Directive 2010/63 is missing here as example = 3Rs are in the law in Europe.
31. Line 50: NAMs are not only to reduce animal experiments, they are for having more human relevant data regardless there is already an animal experiment which can be replaced or not. NAMs are not 3Rs and vice versa, yes there are overlaps, but they do not have the same context necessarily. Maybe the authors should consider to define what they are understanding under the term NAMs in the manuscript as well.
32. P3/line 11: “more ethical and sustainable” ? shouldn't it be “more human relevant”
33. Line 24: How does ECVAM maintain access to leading 3Rs journal, this is new for me, please explain it in detail what is really meant.
34. Line 25: Does ECHA really already implement in silico tools in their assessments or do they work on it how to implement ? Please give examples and citations/references.
35. Line 33: Many initiatives, frameworks are missing, e.g. PREPARE guidelines, EU3Rnet, etc.--> here I would suggest to present several regulations, frameworks, initiatives in a table.
36. P4/line 23/24: the phrase “more ethical and precise results” is very much misleading, why it is assumed that non-animal models produce more precise data than animal studies, this is completely not true, it is just a statistical question. This phrase occurs several times and has to be changed, otherwise it is really too superficial and is written

based on an intention which is not justifiable, maybe the authors meant also here something like more human relevant ?

37. Line 48: Why are higher sample sizes needed for livestock research, are there other statistics per treatment groups necessary than for laboratory animals ? Maybe you should add more citations of original research which supports this statement.
38. P5/line 14: what is meant by “these models” exactly ?
39. Line 19: give numbers for this statement, what do you mean exactly by emerging ..with a growing focus, should be less generic and more based on numbers.
40. Line 23: Does Brazil still has these projects, although the pandemic is over, or had Brazil this number of projects ? Additionally, some sentences are missing to make a better transition, why now the vaccine projects are listed as example, and why is it relevant that “only” 1% of clinical trials are related to these ones ?
41. Lines 38-42: the context is not clear enough, please clarify it or add introductory sentences why you present this here.
42. Line 51: language of the sentence should be improved, and if it is only possible to be calculated why not provide the calculated data ?
43. P6/line 12: total numbers or estimate of it is missing, could be also compared to European animal experimental numbers, could be also deduced from world-wise numbers and subtract European, USA and Asian estimates.
44. Line 14: exchange “than” with “that”
45. Lines 28-33: numbers for latin America could be estimated by subtraction from the world numbers and numbers from other known regions.
46. Line 51: this could be compared to the legal framework in EU, USA, GB, Asian countries.

47. P7/line 12: which bans are really implemented as laws
48. Line 15: again “precise results” change accordingly, see above.
49. Line 32: no numbers available ?
50. Line 36: the reference is not very current.
51. Line 39: the spread of bioethical...began later compared to what or which region; and when did it start ?
52. P8/line 15/16: which sectors are meant, provide more concrete information
53. Line 18: “abuse in research”; which ones, provide examples and references.
54. Line 25: ..”in many institutions”, what does many mean ? provide numbers, where are these institutes.
55. Line 30: “to prioritize” for which reason they prioritize for which activity ? This is unclear.
56. Line 36: information is too vague.
57. Line 41: which networks, who, how many ?
58. Line 51: I would highly recommend not to mix terms like NAMs and non-animal methods; or better define what is exactly meant by which term; explain the differences and how you use this terms.
59. P9/line 23-28: it is unclear which challenges they faced, be more precise.
60. Line 38: what is the name of the mentioned journal, is there a website of it which can be given ?

61. P10/line 22: are website addresses available, if yes, please add them.
62. Line 34: there are no other initiatives worthy to be mentioned ? maybe also academic initiatives; what is about e.g. FIOCRUZ in Brazil, these institutions are also quite significantly active in the 3Rs field.
63. Next Pages 11-33: It is highly recommended to summarize these information in the form of tables otherwise it is very hard for the reader to structurally come through the information, maybe one table for each category and summarize there the information of all countries.
64. Page 33/line 45: where, which regulatory gaps are meant here, be more concrete
65. Line 51: what is about bottom-up developed networks ?

4. Reader engagement

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

No comments specifically on reader engagement.

5. Length and language

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

There are important issues to address around how the authors handle their conflict of interest or objectivity when writing about their own organisation, how they describe the work of other organisations (which ties back to the methods the authors used for acquiring the information they report in this manuscript). Given the manuscript is also very long, restructuring aiming at improving conciseness may also solve some of the challenges raised around tone and interest.

Reviewer comments

Editor (inserted from triage report)

66. On page 10, for the section on Te Protejo, the tone is a bit different - I guess because this is the authors' own organisation, so there is a different attitude and level of familiarity as for other organisations. On the other hand, there is a clear way in which the authors' interests are a conflict for this section. It probably cannot be avoided, but it should be

declared, and a more minimalist and objective tone and set of observations would be appropriate (e.g. other organisations are described functionally but not necessarily credited with “driving” anything in particular, or have their products and programmes described with adjectives (“accessible”, “central role” etc.) which could be removed.

67. The section on Luyef Biotechnology (p19) contains text that sounds like quotes from marketing material. At the very least, the authors should quote as such (e.g. Luyef Biotechnology states on its website that it has a goal of “enabling sustainable, ethica;, and high-performance [etc]”. The question I had about why the specific companies have been highlighted in the way they have still applies, and I wonder if enough is being done to be generally informative about the use of animals and alternative test methods in Latin America - a few case examples without broader context is probably not enough.
68. I felt that by page 19 the article is getting very long - the authors seem to be running out of energy, as each section gets noticeably shorter from around here, and I expect the reader may also start to get fatigued. I wonder if there is a way of providing more succinct summaries of the national situations, which also addresses some of my comments above? For example, the authors could structure the section on Brazil something like as follows, to provide an academic and comprehensive summary of the animal and alternatives situation:

"Brazil is governed by four regulations that have a specific impact on use of animals (short list, explanation of each). The use of animals is regulated by 3 institutions (short list, explanation of each). The major users of animals, at least on the official and better-regulated end of the market, are XYZ. We have little information about the unregulated end. There is a relatively large industry for non-animal test methods compared to other countries, but there are still relatively few companies in this space (XX in total). Examples of the larger companies include XYZ. Examples of smaller companies include XX. They have a turnover of XX according to tax records. XX numbers of ethical violations have been recorded, mostly centred on the smaller end of the market [I don't know if that would be true, it is just an example]."

6. Other comments

Editor's summary of reviewer comments and suggestions for responding

No other comments.

7. Comments on summary sections

Reviewer comments

Reviewer 3

69. Abstract: line 33: it is unclear about which progress is spoken, maybe just delete the first part of the sentence, and just state: the region rely heavily on animal models....

70. Abstract: line 37: towards which improvement ? this is unclear.

71. Abstract: line 42: explain the term NAM in the abstract/use the full word and not the abbreviation at the first time

72. Abstract: 3Rs is missing in this context in the abstract

73. Keywords: 3Rs/ Three 3Rs is missing in the key words

8. Minor issues

Reviewer comments

Editor (inserted from triage report)

74. Minor comment, but the paragraph starting "The initiatives of these organisations" (p10, in "Te Protejo" section) does not belong with the previous paragraph. It should either be in the introduction of the section to front-load the argument, or given a subheading indicating it is a summary of the section. In general, the authors should check that the way they have structured the sections of their manuscript reinforce its narrative flow.

Reviewer 3

75. Addresses of Te Protejo is missing in the affiliation

